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ANALYSIS OF VERTICAL MOVEMENTS OF THE EARTH'S SURFACE IN THE ZONE OF INTERSECTION BETWEEN KARJANTAU AND TAVAKSAY FAULTS OF THE WESTERN TIEN-SHAN

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ABSTRACT

The article has considered analysis of vertical movements of the earth's surface in the zone of intersection between faults of Karjantau and Tavaksay of the Western Tien-Shan. Presented are the results of tachometric measurements carried out in 2016-2017 and leveling works carried out in 1979-1980. Discussed are the results of the analysis of the data obtained, characteristic changes in the data of the vertical movements for the last 36 years.

Keywords: *Vertical Movements, Fault, Deformation, Geodetic Marks, Seismicity, Arcgis Technology.*

INTRODUCTION

The study of modern geodynamic regimes of the earth's crust is the most important research aspect of geology, geophysics, geodesy, seismology and other earth Sciences. Modern movements and deformations observed on the Earth's surface are the most important component of complex studies of geodynamic processes currently occurring in the earth's crust such as of the Pamir's and Tien Shan. (Abdullabekov *et al.*, 1996).

The Republic of Uzbekistan, being part of the Central Asian region, in its structural position refers to the territory of the Western Tien Shan. It is subjected to the deforming effects of movement of North and West Central Kazakhstan shield and Turan plates in the East Tarim and in the South of the Ancient Precambrian Indian platform. Interaction and deformation of crustal blocks of the territory, occupied by Uzbekistan is associated with the dynamics of the lithosphere of the entire Pamir-Alai and Tien Shan regions. Therefore, to explain the Genesis of earthquakes, seismic hazard prediction of our territory is necessary. There is a need to ceaselessly conduct comprehensive geological, geophysical and geodetic studies (Khamidov *et al.*, 2014).

The main part of the territory of the Republic of Uzbekistan is located in seismic active zones. The activity of seismic zones is characterized by the activity of deep faults located within it. The seismic activity of the Tashkent geodynamic polygon is closely related to the activity of the deep Karjantau fault. Strong earthquakes occurring in this seismic active zone are related to the active deep fault of Karjantau. It is known that in the zone of deep Karjantau fault during the past 80 years there were 7 strong earthquakes and 41 noticeable earthquakes. These data show high seismic activity of the region and force to conduct permanent geological, geophysical and geodetic studies in this region (Shukurov, 2016; Shukurov, 2016).

In table 1 provides information on some of the most severe earthquakes that occurred on the territory of the Republic of Uzbekistan and in its immediate vicinity.

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Table 1: Catalog of earthquakes over the past 100 years

Number	Date	Coordinate		depth (km)	magnitude	earthquake
		λ	φ			
1.	1912.01.23	41.00	71.64	10	5.2	Namangan
2.	1924.07.06	40.50	73.10	22	6.4	Kurshab
3.	1924.07.12	40.60	73.20	14	6.5	Kurshab
4.	1926.05.28	40.90	73.10	9	5.3	Djalalabad
5.	1927.08.12	41.00	71.60	14	6.0	Namangan
6.	1937.12.18	42.10	70.90	25	6.5	Pskem
7.	1942.02.14	40.90	72.10	15	5.5	Paytok
8.	1942.01.18	41.10	71.60	21	5.9	Yartepa
9.	1946.11.02	41.90	72.00	30	7.5	Chatkal
10.	1959.10.24	41,67	70.00	13	5,7	Brichmulla
11.	1965.10.13	40.83	69.33	12	5.5	Kashtepa
12.	1966.04.26	41.33	69.28	8	5.3	Tashkent
13.	1967.05.18	40.63	70.75	6	4.6	Supetau
14.	1976.04.08	40.33	63.67	30	7.0	Gazli
15.	1976.04.08	40.28	63.38	30	7.3	Gazli
16.	1977.01.31	40.05	70.52	20	5.7	Isfara-Batken
17.	1977.12.06.	41.58	69.68	15	5.3	Tavaksay
18.	1978.03.17	41.76	64.63	10	6.6	Tamdi
19.	1978.06.04	40.40	63.62	15	6.0	Kizilkum
20.	1980.12.11	41.33	69.05	10	5.2	Nazarbek
21.	1980.12.30	41.31	69.11	10	4.8	Nazarbek
22.	1982.06.10	41.35	69.06	10	5.8	Chimiyon
23.	1984.03.20	40.20	63.11	15	7.2	Gazli
24.	1984.02.17	40.85	71.00	15	5.6	Pop
25.	1985.06.01	41.32	69.11	5	5.5	Kayrokkum
26.	1987.03.26	41.81	69.95	5	5.0	Oltintepa
27.	1987.10.18	42.18	70.10	20	4.0	Angren
28.	1988.10.07	41.83	69.28	10	4.0	Shengeldi
29.	1991.05.23	41.34	69.07	15	4.0	Keles
30.	1992.05.15	40.98	72.38	26	5.5	Izboskan
31.	1992.08.18	42.12	73.61	17	7.5	Susamir

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32.	1994.01.20	41.89	70.26	10	4.5	Pskem
33.	1995.08.19	42.07	70.09	5	4.7	Ugam
34.	2003.04.05	41.10	69.44	5	3.0	Toytepa
35.	2004.12.16	41.23	69.06	5	3.0	Yangiyul
36.	2006.05.01	42.04	69.52	5	3.7	Keles
37.	2006.05.01	42.00	69.50	5	4.0	Keles
38.	2007.07.02	42.32	69.79	5	3.6	Lenger
39.	2008.08.22	41.30	69.40	10	4.7	Tashkent
40.	2010.01.23	41.27	69.19	15	3.3	Toytepa
41.	2013.02.22	41.10	69.10	30	4.6	Yangiyul

Figure 1: Map of seismic activity of Tashkent region and adjacent territories for the period 1912-2013

The results of geophysical, geological, geomorphological, geodetic and other studies confirm that in the territory of the Republic of Uzbekistan modern movements of the earth's crust is characterized by high activity, widespread and continuous tectonic mobility, which is expressed in slow (age-old) and fast (seismic) movements of the earth's crust.

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The study of the internal mechanism of these movements and the nature of modern deformations of the earth's surface is of great scientific and practical importance, contributing to understand the geological and physical essence of the processes occurring in the bowels of the Earth.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Modern movements of the earth's crust - a joint displacement and deformation of the earth's crust, arise at the expense of movement of tectonic plates. This paper expounds the basic prerequisites and methodology of TPS (tachometric) measurements and the current state possibility of the search for precursors, as well as earthquake prediction using example of the territory of Uzbekistan, based on regular observations of crustal deformation.

It is known that to achieve this goal it is necessary to study:

- I. Geological structure of the upper crust;
- II. Modern structure of the earth's crust (the latest and modern tectonics);
- III. Deep structure of the lithosphere;
- IV. General regularities manifestations of geophysical fields and seismicity;
- V. Modern deformation of the earth's crust based on ground and remote regime geodetic observations;
- VI. Features of the manifestation of vertical and horizontal movements of the earth's crust associated natural man-made with destructive processes and phenomena.

One of the main directions of development of geodesy is the study of modern geodynamics by geodetic methods.

The main tasks standing in front of the geodetic service for geodynamics research are:

- I. Doing research on crustal deformation with the identification of the harbinger component before strong earthquakes;
- II. Doing research on the dynamics of vertical and horizontal displacements of the superficial part of the earth's crust determining the location of seismically active faults;
- III. Determination of the intensity of deformation of the earth's surface of the pleistoseist zones, occurred during strong earthquakes, highlighting the residual deformation and clarifying the mechanism of the earthquake source;
- IV. The selection of components deformation of man-made characters and identification of prognostic signs of excited earthquakes in the areas of large hydraulic engineering complexes (Charvak HPP) and in the field of development and operation of oil and gas fields (Gazli, Shurtan, Kandim, Zevarda, Kokdumalak, etc.), located in potentially seismic areas;
- V. Determination of the state of modern crustal movements for recognition and possibility of evaluation of hydrocarbon-containing structures;
- VI. Practical use of the results of seismic and geodynamic research in the creation, restoration and maintenance of the State geodetic and levelling networks, including satellite;
- VII. Doing research on modern vertical and horizontal movements of the earth's crust in large cities, settlements and industrial facilities located in areas of high seismic hazard;
- VIII. Using GPS location, increasing the accuracy and efficiency of the data obtained
- IX. Organization of control and restoration of geodetic networks deformed due to strong earthquakes or intensive modern movements of the earth's crust.

Specialists from the Institute of seismology from the Academy of Sciences of Uzbekistan established a geodynamic polygon. Nowadays on this polygon investigations are conducted on complex geological, geophysical, geodetic aspects.

In 1978, after the earthquake at Tavaksay, D.H.Yakubov and A.R.Yarmukhamedov created geodynamics polygon of Tavaksay . After this following scientists participated in the research work: V.G.Leukhin,

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V.N.Em, R.Ilyasov, A.M.Morokhov, S.A.Irushkin, A.S.Sattarov, Sh.X.Abdullaev, A.R.Yarmukhamedov etc (Yarmukhamedov and Trushkin, 1998; Shukurov, 2013).

Geodetic investigations for the first time on Tavaksay micropolygons was organized by the Institute of seismology under the direction of A.R.Yarmukhamedov in 1978.

Starting in 2016, the renewed integrated geological, geophysical and geodetic studies done on Tavaksay micropolygon. Study was conducted on the geological and tectonic structure, seismicity, the nature of geophysical fields, deep structure, and other data in the zone of deep Karjantau fault and adjacent territories. Profile and areal geomagnetic, geodetic, radiometric researches are carried out; horizontal and vertical movements of the earth crust were investigated. As a result, data was obtained using ArcGIS technologies and a geomorphological model of the territory (DEM-digital elevation model) was given.

Tachometric measurements on Tavaksay micropolygon was conducted based on the local coordinate system. The geodetic marks "Astropunkt" was taken as reference for measurement, at its X-coordinate was of 10,000 meters; the Y-coordinate of 20,000 meters; the Z coordinate was 700 metres away. During field works, the "Astropunkt" and "Ferma" were taken as base marks and all values of the coordinates and the relative heights were determined with reference to them.

Table 2: The results of geodetic measurements in the 2016 - 2017 years

Name geodetic marks	X (1 cycle) 10.04.2016	X (2 cycle) 25.03.2016	Y (1 cycle) 10.04.2016	Y (2 cycle) 25.03.2016	Z (1 cycle) 10.04.2016	Z (2 cycle) 25.03.2016
Noviy	9 815,844	9 815,911	19 292,468	19 292,464	668,443	668,541
Astropunkt	10 000,000	10 000,000	20 000,000	20 000,000	700,000	700,000
Kladbishi	10 202,564	10 202,585	20 665,426	20 665,411	694,902	695,054
Ferma	10 322,543	10 322,550	19 701,238	19 701,232	698,776	698,777
Skala	10 646,937	10 646,954	20 189,155	20 189,108	721,880	721,958
Visota	10 682,756	10 682,777	20 719,951	20 719,913	748,912	749,098

In the leveling measurements in the 1979-1980 years of geodetic marks, "Astropunkt" was taken as reference for all measurements, and its Z-coordinate (height) made at 156,261 meter.

Table 3: The results of geodetic measurements in the 1979 - 1980 years

Name geodetic marks	Z (1 cycle) 22.09.1979	Z (2 cycle) 25.09.1979	Z (3 cycle) 10.05.1980	Z (4 cycle) 29.06.1980	Z (5 cycle) 13.07.1980
Noviy	123,422	123,421	123,421	123,432	123,430
Astropunkt	156,261	156,261	156,262	156,276	156,261
Kladbishi	149,902	149,903	149,892	149,893	149,891
Ferma	153,733	153,731	153,732	153,743	153,721
Skala	176,892	176,888	176,885	176,894	176,880
Visota	203,982	203,985	203,972	203,972	203,970

For the determination of vertical component measured in 1979-1980 (1-5 cycles) and latest in 2016-2017 (0 - 2 cycles) are jointly processed, the results were compared with each other. When processing the data of 1979-1980, the average value of the vertical motion at 5 cycles measured was calculated, and in 2016-2017, the average value of the vertical motion at 2 cycles measured was calculated. All data is transferred in the same coordinate system, are processed using the same methodology.

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Table 4: The results comparison of geodetic marks

Name of geodetic marks	1979, m	2016, m	Difference, m	1979, m	2016, m	1979-2016, m
Noviy	123,422	668,443		667,161	668,443	1,282
Astropunkt	156,261	700,000	543,739	700,000	700,000	0,000
Kladbishi	149,902	694,902		693,641	694,902	1,261
Ferma	153,733	698,776		697,472	698,776	1,304
Skala	176,892	721,880		720,631	721,880	1,249
Visota	203,982	748,912		747,721	748,912	1,191

The results of the study is shown in Table 4, if the difference in the relative height of 1979-2016 subtracted the height of the SGN (State geodetic network) construction ($h = 1.25$ m), then we obtain 36 annual vertical movements of the observation geodetic marks.

Table 5: The value geodetic marks for 36 years

Name geodetic marks	1979, m	2016, m	1979-2016, m	Height of constructions	The difference values for 36 years, m
Noviy	667,161	668,443	1,282	1,250	0,032
Astropunkt	700,000	700,000	0,000	0,000	0,000
Kladbishi	693,641	694,902	1,261	1,250	0,011
Ferma	697,472	698,776	1,304	1,250	0,054
Skala	720,631	721,880	1,249	1,250	-0,001
Visota	747,721	748,912	1,191	1,250	-0,059

Figure 2: Map of vertical movements of geodetic marks on geodynamic polygon Tavaksay

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RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The results thus measured shows changes in the values of vertical movements for the last 36 years at zone of intersection of faults of Karjantau and Tavaksay in the Western Tien-Shan.

In the geodetic marks "Skala" and "Visota", located in the North of the Karjantau fault, there is a lowering of the earth's crust, respectively, by -1 mm and -59 mm. On the points "Noviy", "Kladbishi" and "Ferma", located south of the fault, there occurred a rising of the earth's crust, respectively, by 32 mm, 11 mm and 54 mm.

The results of studies conducted in 2016-2017 at the zone of intersection of Karjantau and Tavaksay faults showed that the vertical movement at the geodetic marks "Ferma" and "Visota" changed more than at other points (Yusupov *et al.*, 2016). These significant changes, in our opinion, show the dynamics of the Karjantau fault activity, since both of these points are located directly in the fault zone.

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